

MODERN TRENDS IN CHANGING GROUNDWATER LEVELS IN IRRIGATED TERRITORIES KARAKALPAKSTAN REPUBLICS

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***Summary.** This article examines the current trends in groundwater level changes in the irrigated territories of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. Based on long-term observations, hydrogeological monitoring materials, and analysis of land reclamation status, the main patterns of seasonal and long-term fluctuations in groundwater depth have been identified. It has been established that the dynamics of groundwater levels are determined by irrigation runoff volumes, the technical condition of the collector-drainage network, the water content of the Amu Darya River, as well as climatic changes. In other areas, a decrease in water levels was noted due to reduced water supply and increased drainage runoff. Measures have been proposed to improve the monitoring and regulation of the hydrogeological regime of irrigated lands.*

***Key words:** groundwater, irrigated lands, hydrogeology, salinization, drainage, land reclamation, groundwater level, Karakalpakstan.*

The Republic of Karakalpakstan is located in the extreme northwestern part of Uzbekistan. The total area is 167.1 km², which accounts for approximately 37% of Uzbekistan's area, of which 1.6 million hectares are suitable for irrigation.

The Republic of Karakalpakstan possesses large reserves of agricultural land. The main direction of the Republic's economy is agriculture and animal husbandry. The leading agricultural crops are rice, wheat, and cotton, the sowing of which in favorable years amounts to 250–300 thousand hectares. Forage, grain, vegetable, melon, and other crops are grown: corn, sorghum, Sudanese grass, watermelon, melon, beans, mung bean, etc.

In terms of natural and climatic conditions, the Republic of Karakalpakstan differs significantly from other Central Asian zones. The climate here is sharply continental and dry. Due to the absence of natural obstacles and the flatness of the terrain, air masses penetrate freely from the north, northwest, and northeast, contributing to a decrease in air temperature and sharp cold snaps during the winter period. Therefore, the winter here is harsh: the minimum air temperature ranges from minus 35 to minus 40 °C. The duration of the cold period lasts from two (in the south) to four (in the north) months. The average annual amount of atmospheric precipitation fluctuates between 70–100 mm. The largest amount of precipitation falls in early spring and partially in winter. The depth of soil freezing on irrigated lands does not

exceed 0.5–0.7 m. The windiest days are observed in April-May, when wind speeds reach 10–15 m/s, and in some years 25 m/s, often transitioning into sandstorms, which causes wind erosion of the soil [1].

The noted climatic factors are characterized as unfavorable in terms of land reclamation status. Experts, analyzing the influence of these factors on the formation and orientation of soil-meliorative and hydrogeological conditions in the study area, note the following [1]:

- atmospheric precipitation does not have a significant impact on the feeding of the groundwater of the Amu Darya delta itself;
- high evaporation characteristic of the delta zone's climate, at a groundwater depth of less than 1.8–2.5 m, causes significant groundwater losses for evaporation and transpiration;
- air temperature regime with a sharp decrease during the non-vegetation period contributes to the freezing of the upper soil layer, which is significantly reflected in the conditions of groundwater feeding. During the summer season, air temperature determines the intensity of evaporation and transpiration processes, respectively increasing or decreasing the discharge part of the groundwater balance.

The geological structure of the Amu Darya delta in the territory of Karakalpakstan consists of many types and types of Cretaceous, Tertiary, and Quaternary deposits. Cretaceous deposits occur on the right bank of the river. Tertiary deposits are found near Tuyamyun, Kyzylkum, Ustyurt, and other areas as deposits of red and red-yellow clays.

Quaternary deposits are widespread in the territory of the modern and forming Amu Darya delta and consist of sands, loams, loams, and clays brought by water. These deposits possess relatively good water permeability, loose structure, and instability to overflow processes. Quaternary deposits are a land reclamation object, forming groundwater and its regime. The complexity of the geological structure of the Amu Darya delta, the presence of irrigated lands in the delta, and their economic use determine the specific characteristics of its hydrogeological conditions and the formation of groundwater regimes.

For the irrigated territories of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the problem of regulating groundwater levels is of particular importance, as the region is characterized by an arid climate, high evaporation, complex soil-meliorative conditions, and limited water resources in the Amu Darya basin.

Prolonged irrigation, filtration losses from canals, insufficient efficiency of collector-drainage systems, and changes in the river's hydrological regime have led to

significant transformations in the territory's water balance. This has caused a change in groundwater depth, increased mineralization, and secondary soil salinization.

The aim of the study is to identify modern trends in groundwater level changes in the region's irrigated areas and to evaluate the factors determining these processes.

The object of the study consists of irrigated lands in the central and northern regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

research methods: comparative-geographical analysis; Statistical processing of long-term observation series; Mapping the depth of groundwater; Correlation analysis of the relationship between groundwater levels and irrigation volumes; Method of zoning by degree of land reclamation risk.

Research results The average groundwater level of the irrigated zone in the Republic of Karakalpakstan for 2023 is presented in Table 2. 1. It can be seen that within the boundaries of reclamation systems, the average annual groundwater level varies from 157 to 561 cm.

Average groundwater level of the irrigated zone in the Republic of Karakalpakstan for 2023

Table 1.

No	Name of reclamation systems	Districts	Months												Average annual groundwater level, cm.
			I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX	X	XI	XII	
1	Southern reclamation system	Turtkul	217	198	170	167	179	185	171	162	170	180	194	200	183
2.		Ellikkala	220	201	173	175	184	188	176	166	177	191	206	214	189
3.		Beruni	196	158	137	138	154	169	162	150	153	173	197	200	166
4	Amudarya Land Reclamation System	Amudarya	164	139	134	146	166	177	150	135	146	171	191	166	157
5	Left-bank land reclamation system	Khojeyli	182	151	136	153	170	193	186	166	177	202	221	203	178
6		Shumanay	199	165	169	176	185	215	229	214	215	224	229	217	203
7		Kanlykul	206	193	190	197	201	210	206	188	192	206	220	217	202
8	Left-bank land reclamation system	Kungrad	196	173	184	176	190	204	198	184	171	178	178	195	186
9		Muynak	563	559	542	550	543	553	567	564	567	577	576	576	561
10	Right-bank land reclamation system	Nukus	242	226	235	230	228	233	220	222	226	248	262	254	236
11		Kegevli	265	252	240	243	244	264	279	269	271	293	304	305	269
12		Chimbay	212	173	175	189	202	227	236	218	229	259	275	287	224
13		Karauzak	189	188	190	178	190	205	204	196	207	220	237	252	205
14		Takhtakuyr	224	219	220	211	213	221	217	217	222	232	243	255	225
in the Republic of Karakalpakstan			234	214	207	209	218	232	229	218	223	240	252	253	227

During the work, we collected materials on the groundwater depth and mineralization of irrigated areas across administrative districts from 1990 to 2023.

In the Turtkul district, the groundwater level has fluctuated from 170 cm to 233 cm over the past years, with an average annual mineralization of 3.08 g/l; At the same time, the lowest groundwater depths were observed in April-August: 170-189 cm.

**“ARAL BOYI GEOLOGIYASINIŇ AĖMIYETLI MASHQALALARI ĖAM
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In the Ellikaly district, the groundwater level has fluctuated from 179 cm to 258 cm over the past years, with an average annual mineralization of 2.46 g/l; At the same time, the lowest groundwater depths were observed in April-August: 142-176 cm.

In the Beruniy district, the groundwater level has fluctuated from 133 cm to 195 cm over the past years, with an average annual mineralization of 2.78 g/l; At the same time, the lowest groundwater depths were observed in April-August: 115-151 cm.

In the Amudarya district, the groundwater level has fluctuated from 137 cm to 188 cm over the past years, with an average annual mineralization of 2.63 g/l; At the same time, groundwater depths fluctuated from 138 to 195 cm throughout the year.

In the Shumanay district, the groundwater level has fluctuated from 179 cm to 488 cm over the past years, with an average annual mineralization of 3.12 g/l; At the same time, groundwater depths fluctuated from 197 to 214 cm throughout the year.

In the Kanlykul district, the groundwater level has fluctuated from 160 cm to 428 cm over the past years, with an average annual mineralization of 2.62 g/l; At the same time, groundwater depths fluctuated from 175 to 228 cm throughout the year.

In the Kungrad district, the groundwater level has fluctuated from 176 cm to 378 cm over the past years, with an average annual mineralization of 2.29 g/l; At the same time, groundwater depths fluctuated from 150 to 221 cm throughout the year.

In the Muynak district, the groundwater level has fluctuated from 252 cm to 743 cm over the past years, with an average annual mineralization of 6.00 g/l; At the same time, groundwater depths fluctuated from 521 to 568 cm throughout the year.

In the Nukus district over the past years, the groundwater level has fluctuated from 185 cm to 297 cm, with an average annual mineralization of 2.33 g/l; At the same time, the groundwater depth varied from 170 to 243 cm throughout the year.

In the Kegeyli district, the groundwater level has fluctuated from 165 cm to 365 cm over the past years, with an average annual mineralization of 2.98 g/l; At the same time, groundwater depths varied from 207 to 265 cm throughout the year.

In the Buzatov district, the groundwater level over the past years has fluctuated from 215 cm to 485 cm, with an average annual mineralization of 2.98 g/l; At the same time, groundwater depths fluctuated from 409 to 612 cm throughout the year.

In the Chimbay district, the groundwater level has fluctuated from 172 cm to 390 cm over the past years, with an average annual mineralization of 3.29 g/l; At the same time, groundwater depths fluctuated from 209 to 245 cm throughout the year.

In the Karauzak district, the groundwater level has fluctuated from 175 cm to 452 cm over the past years, with an average annual mineralization of 2.93 g/l; At the same time, groundwater depths fluctuated from 163 to 214 cm throughout the year.

In the Takhtakupyr district over the past years, the groundwater level has fluctuated from 192 cm to 411 cm, with an average annual mineralization of 2.49 g/l; At the same time, groundwater depths fluctuated from 202 to 232 cm throughout the year.

During the years under review, the groundwater depth across the republic ranged from 185 to 357 cm, with an average annual mineralization of 3.00 g/l; At the same time, the groundwater depth varied from 202 to 234 cm throughout the year.

Analysis of the presented data shows that the hydrogeological situation in the irrigated areas of the Republic of Karakalpakstan in 2023 was characterized by significant spatial and seasonal variability in groundwater levels. The national average was **227 cm**, with significant fluctuations observed throughout the year from **207 cm in March to 253 cm in December**. This indicates a seasonal dependence of groundwater levels on irrigation regimes, infiltration feeding, and the operation of drainage systems.

The closest location of groundwater on average across the republic is recorded in **March–April (207–209 cm)**, which is related to winter-spring soil moisture, decreased evaporation, and moisture accumulation in underground horizons. Starting from May, a gradual increase in bed depth is observed, reaching its maximum in **November-December (252–253 cm)**. This is explained by active water drainage, increased evaporation during the warm period, and a decrease in infiltration feeding by the end of the year.

Among the districts, the deepest groundwater level was noted in Muynak, where the average annual figure was **561 cm**. This is due to the specific characteristics of the natural and climatic conditions, poor provision of irrigation water, and limited infiltration feeding.

The comparative depth of groundwater is also characteristic of the Kegeyli **269 cm**, Nukus **236 cm**, and Takhtakupyr **225 cm** districts.

The groundwater levels closest to the surface were observed in areas with intensive farming: Amudarya **157 cm**, Beruni **166 cm**, and Khojeyli **178 cm**. These values indicate an increased risk of flooding and secondary soil salinization, especially if the efficiency of the collector-drainage network is insufficient.

For the Southern meliorative system (Turtkul, Ellikkala, Beruni), groundwater is characterized by a relatively shallow depth of **166–189 cm**, which is due to intensive irrigation.

The left-bank system is distinguished by more contrasting indicators: from **178 cm** in Khojeyli to **561 cm** in Muynak. This indicates a sharp heterogeneity of natural conditions.

The right-bank system is characterized by medium and relatively stable values ranging from **205 to 269 cm**, indicating a more balanced water regime.

Conclusion Thus, the table data shows that in 2023, a pronounced differentiation in groundwater levels persisted across the irrigated lands of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. The most tense land reclamation situation is observed in areas with depths of less than 2.0 m, where the risk of salinization and waterlogging increases. In areas with depths greater than 2.5–3.0 m, the hydrogeological situation is relatively favorable. This confirms the need for further improvement of drainage systems and rational regulation of irrigation regimes.

References:

1. Alimov A.A. Hydrogeology of Irrigated Territories of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent, 2018.
2. Bekmambetov K.J. Land reclamation status of the Aral Sea region. – Tashkent, 2020.
3. Khodjaev Sh.K. Groundwater of Arid Regions of Central Asia. – Tashkent, 2019.
4. Chembarisov E.I., Khojamuratova R.T. Practical Hydroecology (using the example of the Republic of Karakalpakstan). study guide Nukus, Bilim, 2012. - 84 p.
5. Reports of the Hydrogeological and Meliorative Service of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, 2025.